

ISic0063

I.Sicily inscription 0063

Language

Latin

Type

honorific; building

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Imp(erator) Caesar divi Nervae
2. f(ilius) Nerva Traianus Aug(ustus)
3. Germanicus Dacicus
4. pontifex maximus
5. tr(ibunicia) pot(estate) VII imp(erator) IIII
6. co(n)s(ul) V p(ater) p(atriciae)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175834

EDR 094013

EDCS 22100591

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7472 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650805>)

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Raepsaet-Charlier, M.-Th. 1974. A propos du récent catalogue d'inscriptions latines du musée de Palerme. *Latomus*. 33: 124-127. At 126

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 71 no.2 fig.32

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